

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№4(1)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 754 sahifa,
2-aprel, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Yangi O'zbekistonning mintaqaviy va global geosiyosiy pozitsiyasi: milliy o'zlik va media reprezentatsiya tahlili	16
Salim Doniyorov	
Axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari vositasida o'quvchilarning adabiy tahlil kompetensiyasini shakllantirish	21
Djo'rayev Yorqin Xolnizozovich, Xoldarova Gulchehra Tajibayevna	
Adabiy tahlil kompetensiyasini shakllantirishda elektron darsliklar va multimedia vositalaridan foydalanish.....	26
Djo'rayev Yorqin Xolnizozovich	
Ta'limdagi hurfikrlikni rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	29
Yunusov Dilshod Raxmatovich	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarda tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	32
Aliqulova Habiba Bahranovna	
Ayollar boksida jismoniy tayyorgarlikning yosh qizlar salomatligiga ta'siri	36
Majidov Ruslan Rustam o'g'li, Komilova Ismigul O'ktamjon qizi	
Talaba-yoshlarda internet risklarning oldini olishning pedagogik modeli	41
Muradova Maftuna Komilovna, Mamadaliyeva Umida Isroiljonovna	
Диагностика креативности студентов педагогических вузов в процессе изучения специальных дисциплин.....	44
Уразова Марина Батыровна, Соибова Толифа Дилмуродовна	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kommunikativ kompetentlikni shakllantirishning metodik xususiyatlari.....	49
Tashibekova Munajat Xoshimovna	
Mariya Montessori ta'limida bolalarning mustaqilligini va ijodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-didaktik shart-sharoitlari.....	53
Asqarova Ma'mura Sadriddinovna	
O'spirinlik yoshida namoyon bo'ladigan agressiv xulqning psixologik xususiyati	59
Atajanova Xurjon Pirnazar qizi	
O'zbekiston jurnalistikasining rivojlanishida jadidlarning o'rni: jurnalistikada yangi trend	64
Murtozayeva Nigora Murtoza qizi	
Virtual ta'lim texnologiyasining ta'lim jarayonini takomillashtirishdagi ahamiyati.....	67
Muxsiyeva Aziza Shamsitdinovna	
Kelajakdagi o'qituvchilarning pedagogik kreativligini ta'limiy o'yinlar orqali rivojlantirish yo'llari	69
N. A. Musayeva	
Talabalarda lisoniy tafakkurni shakllantirishga psixolingvistik yondashuvning didaktik tamoyillari	76
Odiljonova Kamola Abduvosit qizi	
Strategies for Overcoming Difficulties in Using Authentic Materials in English Language Teaching	81
Qosimov Jaloliddin Abduvali o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	84
Qurbonova Buzaynab Nurmuxammadiyevna	
Inspektor-psixologlarda ijtimoiy-psixologik kompetentlikning kasbiy faoliyatdagi ahamiyati	87
Raxmanova Dilnoza Farmanovna	
Qo'ng'iro't tumani toponimlarining leksik-semantik va genetik xususiyatlari	90
Shamshaddinova Saodat Saparbayevna	
Variativ yondashuv asosida 5–9-sinf o'quvchilarida valeologik madaniyatni rivojlantirishning didaktik modeli va metodik ta'minoti	93
Shamuratov Asqar Abdullayevich	

The Structural Composition and Developmental Stages of Critical Thinking Skills.....	98
<i>Shuxratjon Ismoiljonov Boymirza o'g'li</i>	
Yosh rahbar kadrlarni lavozimlarga tayinlashning psixologik xususiyatlari.....	106
<i>Sobitov Otabek</i>	
O'zbekistonda erta turmush qurish masalasi va uning psixologik tahlillari.....	111
<i>Sodiqova Gulbarno Odiljon qizi</i>	
Adaptiv sportning inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida alohida ta'limga ehtiyoji bo'lgan o'quvchilarning jismoniy va funksional rivojlanishidagi ahamiyati.....	114
<i>Xasanova Sarvinov To'liqinjon qizi</i>	
Yosh futbolchilarda texnik mahoratni rivojlantirishda differentsiallashgan mashg'ulotlar modelini qo'llash samaradorligi	118
<i>Zayniddinov Tojiddin Baxriddinovich</i>	
Фразеологизмы как носители культуры: проблемы перевода и методы обучения	123
<i>Хамидова Гулноза Турсунбой кизи</i>	
Talabalarni kreativ yondashuv asosida tarbiyaviy–innovatsion faoliyatga tayyorlash jarayonlari.....	127
<i>Adizova G. M.</i>	
Iqtidorli bolalarni psixologik-pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlash	131
<i>Ismoilova Adolat Anvarovna</i>	
STEAM – ta'lim texnologiyasi asosida o'quvchilarning fazoviy tasavvurlarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	134
<i>So'fiboyeva Gulchehra Mamurjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy ko'nikmalar va kompetentlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	138
<i>Fayzullayeva Xovoxon Xayrullo qizi</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'limga muhtoj bolalar bilan ishlashda tarbiyachining roli.....	142
<i>Mansurova Lobar Luqmon qizi, Boqiyeva E'zoza Mashrab qizi</i>	
Rivojlanishida nuqsoni bor bolalarni ta'lim-tarbiyalashning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari.....	146
<i>Tojiboyeva Osiyoxon Alisher qizi</i>	
Xalqaro ta'lim tashkilotlari faoliyatining nazariy asoslari.....	150
<i>Abdusamadova Aziza Kamoliddin qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni ijtimoiy texnologiyalar asosida ijtimoiy-pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash tizimi sifatida.....	153
<i>Shanazarov Otabek</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda STEAM yondashuvini loyiha asosida joriy etishning pedagogik strategiyalari	158
<i>Radjapova Xuzra Tirkashevna, Abdullayeva Sarviniso</i>	
Matematika ta'limida modellashtirishning psixologik va metodik asoslari: disum loyihasi tahlili.....	161
<i>Xaydarov Xurshid Ismatovich</i>	
Darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda gandbolchilarning tezkorligini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	166
<i>Ismatullayeva Zuhra Rustam qizi</i>	
Osiyo xalq o'yinlari asosida jismoniy tarbiya jarayonini samarali tashkil etishning pedagogik shartlari	170
<i>Abdullayev Yashnarjon Mahkamovich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning innovatsion kompetentligini shakllantirishda klasterli ta'lim muhitining imkoniyatlari.....	173
<i>Abduraxmanov M. B.</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida tanqidiy fikrlash.....	178
<i>Chinaliyeva Ayjamal Baxitjanovna</i>	
Talabalarda raqamli ta'lim madaniyatini rivojlantirish.....	181
<i>Eshqurbonova Nafisa Bahodir qizi</i>	
Blended Educational Technologies in Higher Education: A Systematic Analysis of Foreign Research.....	183
<i>Fozilova Maxina Adashevna</i>	
Voyaga yetmaganlarda deviant xulq shakllanishida ijtimoiy-psixologik omillarning roli.....	188
<i>Galdiyeva Mehribon Durdiyevna, Saydazimov Alisher Nurali o'g'li</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Boshlang'ich tayyorlov guruhida ulotqirish texnikasi elementlarini o'rgatish samaradorligi.....	191
	Hayitmurodova Nasiba Abdusalimovna	
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida tarbiya fanini o'qitishning metodik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish zaruriyati.....	197
	Inoyatova Zulfiya Xamdammovna	
	Talabalarni ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyatiga jalb etishning metodologik asoslari.....	199
	Karimova Madinabonu Dilshodbek qizi	
	Kompetentligini baholash mezonlari va indikatorlarini ishlab chiqish.....	203
	Kayumov Oybek Achilovich	
	Kasbiy refleksiya asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning pedagogik mahoratini rivojlantirish.....	209
	Miraxmedova Mubina Mirxalil qizi	
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.....	211
	Nisanbayeva Akmaral Kaldibayevna	
	Maxsus ta'lim dasturlari orqali iqtidorli talabalarining ijodiy salohiyatini rivojlantirish.....	214
	Rayimova Shahlo Sobirjon qizi	
	STEAM ta'limida ijtimoiy intellektni rivojlantirish metodlari.....	217
	Toshev Elbek Choriyevich	
	Innovatsion texnologiyalar va ularning tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarini tayyorlash tizimidagi roli.....	223
	Usmanov Botir Allaberdiyevich	
	Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning ijtimoiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda volontyorlik faoliyatining ahamiyati.....	227
	Xalilova Dilnoza Furkatovna	
	Boshlang'ich sinflarda robototexnikaning ahamiyati va o'rni.....	230
	Xodiyeva Dilrabo Pirimovna	
	Working With Visual AIDS in Teaching English in Primary Education.....	233
	Yunusova Nodira Akhmadjanovna	
	Teatr texnologiyalarini maktabgacha ta'limga integratsiya qilishning pedagogik shartlari.....	237
	Abdullayeva Aziza Abdurazzoq qizi, Salimova Dilmira Farxodovna	
	The Psychological Impact of Social Media on Youth.....	242
	Dilfuza Qarshiboyeva	
	Maktab direktori nutq etiketi – ta'lim menejmentida jamoatchilik bilan samarali muloqot asosi.....	246
	Islamova Dilfuza Dilshodovna	
	Dizartriyali bolalar monologik nutqini innovatsion texnologiyalar orqali rivojlantirish.....	250
	Pardayeva Muxlisa	
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar rivojlanishida bilish jarayonlarning ahamiyati.....	257
	Xaydarova Umidaxon Baxromjon qizi	
	Enhancing the Professional Competence of English Language Teachers.....	259
	Karimova Dilshoda Sodiqjon qizi	
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda montessori metodi bo'yicha sezgir davrlar.....	264
	Tojiakhmedova Maftuna Umarjon qizi	
	"Personal learning assistant" vositalari asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarni tayyorlash tizimidagi zamonaviy tendensiyalar tahlili.....	268
	Muradova Maftuna Komilovna, Turobova Ro'zoy Bekmurotovna, Xayrullayev Mo'minbek Anvar o'g'li	
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish savodxonligi darslarida adabiy-nutqiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish metodikasi.....	272
	Ravshanova Dildora Sagdullayevna	
	Raqamli ta'lim sharoitida elektron axborot-ta'lim muhitining mohiyati va tarkibiy tuzilmasi.....	279
	Temurov Sobirjon Yo'ldoshevich	
	Zamonaviy ta'lim menejmentida innovatsion yondashuvlarning ahamiyati (boshlang'ich ta'lim misolida).....	283
	Pardaboyev Doston	
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va oilaning hamkorligida qadriyatlar tarbiyasining amaliy asoslari.....	286
	Xaydarova Mavluda Mo'yidinjon qizi	

Zamonaviy pedagogik va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari integratsiyasi asosida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish bosqichlari va samarali shakllari.....	292
<i>G'oziyeva Mohlaroyim Qodirxon qizi</i>	
Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojiga ega bo'lgan bolalarning (aqliy nuqson) ovqatlanish tartibi	295
<i>Sh. M. Ro'ziyeva</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda ona tili darslarida imlo savodxonligini oshirishda geymifikatsiya o'yini orqali samarali tashkil etish	299
<i>Mergenbaeva Asiya Erkebaevna</i>	
Musiqqa o'qituvchisining pedagogik muloqatining ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati	304
<i>S. M. Raxmonberdiyeva</i>	
Ijtimoiy-maishiy hayotga yo'naltirish darslarida zaif eshituvchi o'quvchilarning nutqini rivojlantirish	307
<i>Abdulxamidova Gulnoza</i>	
Ispaniya davlati ijtimoiy hayoti, madaniyati va o'ziga xos ta'lim tizimi	311
<i>Umarova Malika Xisabidinovna, Sabirova Nodira Ibrohimovna</i>	
Ertaklardagi so'zlardan foydalangan holda nutqi rivojlanmagan bolalarda muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish metodologiyasi	316
<i>G'opporova Mahliyoxonim</i>	
Tarbiya fanida hadislar va milliy qadriyatlarni integratsiya qilishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	319
<i>Axmedov Boburjon Vasikovich</i>	
Chaqiriqqacha harbiy ta'lim tizimida o'quv-biluv kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning innovatsion yondashuvlari	324
<i>Mirzayev Shavkat Turdibayevich</i>	
Mustaqil ta'lim olish faoliyati tushunchasining pedagogik mohiyati va tarkibiy tuzilmasi (fizika fani bo'yicha).....	328
<i>Esanmurodov Otamurod Boboqand o'g'li</i>	
Oliy ta'limda immersiv yondashuvning mohiyati.....	333
<i>Muradova Maftuna Komilovna, Jontemirova Nozima Abdijabbor qizi</i>	
Yengil atletika mashg'ulotlari tizimida sportchilarning psixologik tayyorgarligini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari.....	337
<i>Yigitaliyev A. F.</i>	
Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasida o'quvchilarning harakat faolligini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy pedagogik mexanizmlari.....	343
<i>D. R. Abdusalomov</i>	
Futbolchilarni tayyorlash jarayonida innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llashning samaradorligi...	348
<i>Mirbabayev Muzaffar Ismatillayevich</i>	
Empirik tushunchalar va ularning hospital pedagogikadagi pedagogik-psixologik roli	353
<i>Sapayeva Mavluda Shanazarovna</i>	
Ayollarga nisbatan zo'ravonlikka qarshi kurash va huquqiy himoya.....	357
<i>Ibragimova Feruza Bahodirxonovna</i>	
Integrativ yondashuv asosida kongruentlik kompetensiyasini shakllantirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar.....	362
<i>Kamalova Dilobar Tairovna</i>	
Og'ir atletikachilarning ko'p yillik tayyorgarlik jarayonini tashkil etish	366
<i>Raximov Farxod Maxmudovich</i>	
Haqiqiy materiallardan foydalangan holda o'qishni o'rgatish	370
<i>Axmedov Husen Uzairovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda innovatsion va fiziologik yondashuvlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	376
<i>Ruziyeva Gulsara Temirqulovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talaba-yoshlarning jismoniy tarbiyasi.....	380
<i>Nazarov Zokir Abdurahmonovich</i>	
Tafakkur va mantiqiy fikrlash bo'lajak pedagog shaxsining nutq madaniyati omili sifatida	383
<i>A. Sh. Jumayev</i>	
Bo'lajak musiqa o'qituvchilarida turizm vositasida tolerantlikni rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	386
<i>Abdumannatova Aziza Abdumajit qizi</i>	

Zamonaviy didaktik vositalar asosida talabalarning kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	390
<i>Asobayeva Noila Samatovna</i>	
Axborot texnologiyalarini kasbiy faoliyatda qo'llash" fanidan amaliy va laboratoriya mashg'ulotlarini samarali tashkil etish	395
<i>Axmedova Zebixon Siddikovna</i>	
Talaba shaxsini ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalashga qo'yilgan pedagogik talablar	399
<i>Boliyev Uchqun Ismatovich</i>	
Translation of Phraseological Units in Mass Media Texts.....	402
<i>Eshmurodova Ziyodaxon Urinbayevna</i>	
Phraseologisms in Modern Russian: A Corpus-Based Analysis of Structural, Semantic, and Functional Dynamics	405
<i>Farkhod Kholmatov</i>	
Yosh sportchilarda sprinterlik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda o'yin uslubidagi mashqlarning o'rni.....	413
<i>G'oibov Yusufali Buxoraliyevich</i>	
Imitatsion mashqlarni nutqni avtomatizatsiyalash jarayonida qo'llash metodikasi	417
<i>G'aniyeva Muhabbat Lutfullayevna</i>	
1879-1894-yillarda yevropa va aqshdagi asos soluvchi laboratoriyalar evolyutsiyasi orqali eksperimental psixologiya genezisining qiyosiy-tarixiy tahlili.....	420
<i>Haydarov Farhod Imazarovich</i>	
Maktab direktori nutq etiketi – ta'lim menejmentida jamoatchilik bilan samarali muloqot asosi	423
<i>Islamova Dilfuza Dilshodovna</i>	
Bolalarda gigiyeniya qoidalarini o'rgatishning pedagogik ahamiyati	427
<i>Kalkonova Lutfiya Yusufovna, Safarova Qizlarxon</i>	
Kasbiy refleksiya va portfolio metodining ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati	430
<i>Ismoilova Adolat Anvarovna, Kamoliddinova Mahliyoxon Zohidjon qizi</i>	
Практическая работа по развитию логического мышления учащихся начальных классов через дидактические игры	433
<i>Отажонов Ж. М., Мамарасулова М. А.</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida "tarbiya" fanini o'qitish jarayonida mavjud muammolar, ularning sabablari va takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	436
<i>Mamirova Shaxnoza Xudoyqulovna</i>	
Word Formation and Vocabulary Enrichment in Modern English and Uzbek Languages	440
<i>Muminova Feruza Muratdjanovna</i>	
Nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlarining maktabgacha ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni va rivojlanish tendensiyalari	443
<i>Muminova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna</i>	
Shaxs taraqqiyotining turli bosqichlarida refleksiyaning rivojlanishi	447
<i>N. I. Xalilova</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda inklyuziv kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	450
<i>Omanqulova Shohida Nematillo qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarda gender madaniyatni shakllantirishda milliy qadriyatlar va zamonaviy yondashuvning uyg'unligi	455
<i>O'tkirova Zuhraxon Ahmedjanovna</i>	
Developing Listening and Speaking Skills in Middle School	458
<i>Rakhmonova Dilrabokhon Salokhiddin kizi</i>	
Bolalarda gigiyena qoidalarini o'rgatishning pedagogik ahamiyati	461
<i>Kalkonova Lutfiya Yusufovna, Safarova Qizlarxon</i>	
Avlodlar nazariyalari haqidagi mulohazalarning nazariy tahlili: baby boomerlar, X, Y, Z avlodlari.....	464
<i>Umarova Sitora Muxlisovna, Sharifova Mahtob Murodjonovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida kasbiy kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari	467
<i>Abrorxonova Kamolaxon Abrorxon qizi, Sofoyeva Oysha Davlatyorovna</i>	

Boshlang'ich sinflarda arifmetik amallarni o'rgatishning samarali metodlari.....	470
<i>Solijonova Mavluda Zokir qizi</i>	
Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar samaradorligini takomillashtirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	472
<i>Toxirov Botirjon G'ofurjon o'g'li</i>	
Chaqiriqqacha harbiy ta'limda talabalarining harbiy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda psixologik omillarning o'rni.....	477
<i>Tursunov Shaxzod Ramazonovich</i>	
Bolalarning jismoniy faolligini oshirish va jismoniy rivojlantirish bo'yicha noan'anaviy jismoniy mashqlarning ahamiyati	480
<i>Xalmatova Nasiba Bozorboyevna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida ekologik tafakkurni rivojlantirish muammolari.....	485
<i>Yaxshiboyeva Nargiza Rustamqulovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'quv-bilish faolligini rivojlantirishda bolalar adabiyotidan foydalanish ..	488
<i>Yuldoshova Mehriniso Ochildiyevna</i>	
Hosila va uning tatbiqlarini o'rgatishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar	491
<i>Absamatov Zuxriddin Axmad o'g'li</i>	
Развитие речи у детей как ключевой фактор формирования личности.....	496
<i>Дустова Дилдора Собиржановна</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda geometrik tasavvurlarni shakllantirish metodikasi	498
<i>Imamova Nasiba Xurramovna</i>	
Дидактические основы подготовки будущих педагогов к лекционной деятельности.....	501
<i>Нодира Азаматова</i>	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida tarbiyalanuvchilarning ijtimoiy-hissiy rivojlanishini tarkib toptirishning o'ziga xos tamoyillari	505
<i>Mahmudova Zulfiya, Hoshimova Dilnoza</i>	
Musiq ta'limi yo'nalishi talabalarida qo'shiq ijrochiligi malakalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik xususiyatlari	509
<i>Murodov Mirshoxid Burxanovich</i>	
Umummuhandislik fanlarini o'qitish jarayonida muhandislik oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining texnologik kompetentligini shakllantirish	513
<i>Kiyomov Abdulla Xaytaliyevich</i>	
Психолого-педагогический анализ использования исторических материалов на уроках математики в начальных классах.....	520
<i>Джавлиева Гулнара Раушановна</i>	
Transport vositalari muhandisligida virtual reallik va simulyatsiyaga asoslangan ta'lim texnologiyalarini joriy etish: amaliy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishga tizimli yondashuv	529
<i>Tashpulatov Boyburi Baymurotovich</i>	
Adaptiv texnologiyalar va ularning ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni.....	533
<i>Quchqarova Dilnavoz Shaymaxammat qizi</i>	
Talaba-yoshlarda futbol mashg'ulotlari asosida jismoniy tayyorgarlikni rivojlantirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari	538
<i>Alimov Tojiddin Yaxshibayevich</i>	
Milliy madaniy meros asosida talabalarda ijtimoiy va axloqiy mas'uliyatni rivojlantirish.....	542
<i>Nomanov Kozimjon Kamoliddinovich</i>	
Innovatsion o'yinlar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda mayda motorikani rivojlantirish yo'llari	546
<i>Nuritdinova Xurshida Norpulatovna, Azimova Umida To'ra qizi</i>	
Pedagogical opportunities for developing productive skills in english language learning	549
<i>Shohida Otahanova</i>	
Bosh miya o'smasi bo'lgan maktab o'quvchilariga zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanib darslarni tashkil etish	552
<i>Xakimova Gulshat Abdusalomovna, Nurmuhammedova Ruxshoda Mirsodiq qizi</i>	

Traits of Oral Fluid Biochemistry and Physical Chemistry in Children Exhibiting Abnormalities Post-Uranoplasty	557
Anvarova Muhtasar Anvarovna	
O'simliklarning abiotik stresslarga chidamliligini oshirishda crispr/cas texnologiyasining ahamiyati	561
Saidmurodov Saidali Chori o'g'li, Lutfullayev Nodir Abdusattor o'g'li, Turayev Ozod Sunnataliyevich, Dulanzarov Abror Anvar o'g'li, Xayitova Shahlo Davlatovna	
Zamonaviy sharoitlarda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini xorijiy tajribalar asosida boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish	566
Sotimova Barno Marufjonovna	
Tasviriy san'at fanini o'qitishda milliy san'at elementlaridan foydalanishning ayrim metodlari	570
Abdullayev Sayfulla Fayzullayevich, Abdullayev Suxrob Sayfullayevich, Zikrillayeva Visola Hamrayevna	
Метод, основанный на построении симметрии при делении угла с недоступной вершиной	576
Эсонов Мунавваржон Муқимжонович	
Innovatsion yondashuv asosida talabalarni muhandislik faoliyatiga tayyorlash pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	579
Hamraqulov Yorqin Murtazaqulovich	
Internet tizimida muloqotning gendorologik tipologiyasi	584
Raxmonova Barno Odilovna	
Bolalarga xos nutq muhitida etiketning ahamiyati	587
Temirova Nargiza Davlat qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari pedagoglarining kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirishda virtual reallik asosidagi texnologiyalardan foydalanish.....	590
Choriyeva Lobar Fayzullo qizi, Teshaboyeva Zamira Sabirovna, Safarov Azamat Rasul o'g'li	
Hozirgi kun pedagogi.....	594
Dehqanova Muborakxon G'iyeziddin qizi	
"Avesto"dagi ta'limiy-axloqiy qarashlarning nazariy asoslari va pedagogik ahamiyati	598
Ibragimova Farangiza Oybekjon qizi	
Ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida ijtimoiy-pedagogik muammolarning shakllanish omillari va bartaraf etish yo'llari	602
Mirzayeva Faroxat Odiljonovna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini xalqaro reytinglarga tayyorlashda strategik menejmentning o'rni va ahamiyati.	607
Mannonova Barno	
Scientific-Theoretical Bases of Developing Students' Creative Ability Through Folk Practical Art	611
Ruziyeva Mekka Shukhrat kizi	
3-sinf ona tili darslarida integratsion yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarning nutqiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	615
Jurayeva Dildora Ilhom qizi, Mambetova Lobar Mirzavali qizi	
Kurash mashg'ulotlari jarayonida texnik-taktik ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	618
Soatov E. M.	
Talabalarining mustaqil ta'limini tashkil etishga asoslangan dasturiy ta'minot yaratish mohiyati	623
Janabergenova Aysuliy Jaksilikovna	
Maxsus pedagogning kasbiy kompetentligi: zamonaviy yondashuvlar va muammolar	626
Shodiyeva Gulchiroy Nurqosimovna	
O'zbek va qoraqalpoq tillarini integratsiyalashgan holda o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni.....	631
Mapruza Embergenova	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda o'quv-bilish faoliyatini shakllantirishda neyropedagogik usullardan foydalanishning ahamiyati	636
Jumayeva Maxbuba O'ktam qizi	
Inklyuziv ta'lim muhitida musiqa darslarini tashkil etishning uslubiy asoslari	641
Narzikulov Javohir Ikromovich	
Диагностический потенциал формирования критического мышления в оценке нравственной воспитанности студентов педагогических вузов.....	645
Азимова Гулрухбону, Абдувалиева Мухайё	

Musiqa darslarida 4K kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning imkoniyatlari va pedagogik shart-sharoitlari....	652
<i>Ochilova Mohinur</i>	
Oliy ta'limda fransuz tilini o'qitishda qr-kod texnologiyalarining samaradorligi	656
<i>Muzaffarova Nodira Mardonovna</i>	
Смарт-технологии как инструмент повышения эффективности управления	660
<i>Байбаева Мухайё Худайбергеновна, Дехконова Мохларойим Бахтиёржон кизи</i>	
Odam markaziy asab tizimi taraqqiyoti va uni rivojlantirishning amaliy yechimlri.....	664
<i>Mirzayeva Nodira Abduxamidovna</i>	
Mentimeter dasturi va uning ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati.....	669
<i>Djabbarova Xabiba Kuvandikovna</i>	
Talabalarda fuqarolik kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda yangi renessans pedagogikasining o'rni.....	673
<i>Qlicheva Go'zal Chorshanbiyevna</i>	
Kognitiv rivojlanish zamonaviy ta'lim nazariyasida kompleks fenomen sifatida	678
<i>Abdullayeva Madina Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Kursantlarning maxsus chidamkorligini oshirishda qo'llaniladigan vosita va usullar	681
<i>I. B. Bobomuratov</i>	
The Main Aspects of the Development of Digital Literacy in Higher Pedagogical Education	685
<i>Yusupova Go'zal Oybek qizi</i>	
Conceptual Approaches to Understanding Fanaticism Among Female Adolescents.....	689
<i>Sobirova Sojidxon Akramjon qizi</i>	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida basketbol texnika va taktikasini shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	692
<i>Bobojonov Nozimjon Ne'matjonovich, Sirojiddin Nasriddinov Salohiddin o'g'li</i>	
Bolalar musiqa va san'at maktablarida musiqa nazariyasi va solfedjio darslarining pedagogik xususiyatlari	695
<i>Bobojonova Zeboxon Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarida integrativ yondashuv asosida ekologik madaniyatni rivojlantirish ..	699
<i>Istamov Zavqiddin Sa'dulloevich</i>	
Talabalar identiteti va ularga ijtimoiy tarmoqlar ta'sirining global ahamiyati	702
<i>N. T. Tojiboyeva</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya darslarini tashkil etishning zamonaviy usullari	707
<i>Narzullayev Mavlonbek Zikrillo o'g'li, Ostonov Zafar Zamonovich</i>	
Ta'lim metodlari va usullarini modernizatsiya qilish asosida ilmiy tadqiqot madaniyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik tizimi.....	710
<i>Olimov Temir Xasanovich</i>	
Changes in Adolescents' Communication Under the Influence of Social Media: Emotional Intelligence and Internet Addiction Issues	715
<i>Salomov Shamsiddin Sabokhiddin Ugli</i>	
O'smir qizlarning jismoniy rivojlanishini takomillashtirishda defile mashqlaridan foydalanish metodikasi ...	720
<i>Shaxbazova Gulrux Orifjon qizi, Abdullayeva Maxbuba</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablari musiqa madaniyati darslarida o'quvchilarning divergent fikrlashini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	724
<i>Ubaydullayeva Nazokat Ibodullo qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak musiqa o'qituvchilarining pedagogik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish: nazariy asoslar, amaliy modellar va innovatsion yondashuvlar	728
<i>Umurzoqova Laylo Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Talaba-yoshlar jismoniy madaniyat va sportini rivojlantirishning strategik imkoniyatlari	733
<i>Yusupxo'jayev Oxunjon Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
Teatr texnologiyalarini maktabgacha ta'limga integratsiya qilishning pedagogik shartlari.....	737
<i>Abdullayeva Aziza Abdurazzoq qizi, Salimova Dilmira Farxodovna</i>	
Компенсация трудностей в обучении детей младшего школьного возраста, находящихся на длительном лечении	742
<i>Алимова Нигора Исраиловна, Холлиева Нодира Хайтмуратовна</i>	

Формирование профессиональных компетенций будущих художников через освоение узбекского орнамента в системе заданий по композиции.....	745
Д. Б. Бабаева	
Методика и подходы обучения речи в школьной практике	750
Шарипов Одилжлон Гуломжон угли	

CHANGES IN ADOLESCENTS' COMMUNICATION UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA: EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND INTERNET ADDICTION ISSUES

Salomov Shamsiddin Sabokhiddin Ugli

PhD researcher, lecturer, department of applied psychology,
National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article examines how social media influences changes in adolescents' communication, with a particular focus on how internet addiction affects emotional intelligence as an important component of interpersonal interaction. The study involved 520 adolescents aged 18–22, and data were collected using observation, interviews, and psych diagnostic methods. The results revealed a statistically significant negative relationship between the level of internet addiction and emotional intelligence. In particular, a decrease in empathy and the ability to understand others' emotions was directly associated with excessive use of social media. The findings also show that overuse of social media limits adolescents' real-life communication experiences and negatively affects the development of their emotional sensitivity and communication skills. Based on the results, practical recommendations were developed to support the development of emotional intelligence in adolescents and to promote more conscious and balanced use of social media.

Key words: adolescents, social media, communication, emotional intelligence, internet addiction, empathy, digital environment, interpersonal relationships.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ijtimoiy tarmoqlar ta'sirida o'spirinlar muloqotidagi o'zgarishlar, xususan, internetga qaramlikning shaxslararo muloqot jarayonidagi muhim komponent sifatidagi o'rni hamda uning emotsional intellektga ta'siri empirik jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda 18–22 yoshdagi 520 nafar o'spirin ishtirok etib, ma'lumotlar kuzatish, suhbat hamda psixodiagnostik metodlar asosida to'plandi. Olingan natijalar internetga qaramlik darajasi va emotsional intellekt o'rtasida statistik jihatdan ahamiyatli manfiy bog'liqlik mavjudligini ko'rsatdi. Ayniqsa, empatiya va boshqalarning emotsiyalarini idrok etish ko'rsatkichlarining pasayishi ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan ortiqcha foydalanish bilan bevosita bog'liqligi aniqlandi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan haddan tashqari foydalanish o'spirinlarning real muloqot tajribasini cheklab, ularning emotsional sezgirligi va kommunikativ kompetensiyalarining rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalariga asoslangan holda, o'spirinlarning emotsional intellektini rivojlantirish va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan ongli ravishda foydalanish madaniyatini shakllantirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'spirinlar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, muloqot, emotsional intellekt, internetga qaramlik, empatiya, raqamli muhit, shaxslararo munosabatlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье эмпирически анализируются изменения в общении подростков под влиянием социальных сетей, в частности влияние интернет-зависимости на эмоциональный интеллект как важный компонент межличностного взаимодействия. В исследовании приняли участие 520 подростков в возрасте 18–22 лет, данные были собраны с использованием методов наблюдения, интервью и психодиагностических методик. Полученные результаты показали наличие статистически значимой отрицательной связи между уровнем интернет-зависимости и эмоциональным интеллектом. В частности, было установлено, что снижение уровня эмпатии и способности распознавать эмоции других напрямую связано с чрезмерным использованием социальных сетей. Результаты исследования также свидетельствуют о том, что чрезмерное использование социальных сетей ограничивает опыт реального общения подростков и негативно влияет на развитие их эмоциональной чувствительности и коммуникативных навыков. На основе полученных результатов были разработаны практические рекомендации, направленные на развитие эмоционального интеллекта у подростков и формирование культуры осознанного использования социальных сетей.

Ключевые слова: подростки, социальные сети, общение, эмоциональный интеллект, интернет-зависимость, эмпатия, цифровая среда, межличностные отношения.

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, social media has become an important part of adolescents' lives, significantly influencing their communication, social relationships, and psychological development. Studies show that social media has turned into a primary space for communication in adolescents' daily lives, directly shaping their behavior, ways of self-expression, and socialization processes (Piccerillo & Digennaro, 2025) ^[5]. Adolescence is an important stage of emotional and social development, during which emotional intelligence becomes one of the key factors shaping the quality of interpersonal communication. Adolescents with higher levels of emotional intelligence tend to communicate more effectively, manage conflicts better, and adapt more successfully in social situations.

In contrast, lower levels of emotional intelligence have been found to be associated with problematic use of social media (Granda Brito & Sarmiento Benavides, 2025) ^[3]. At the same time, internet addiction is becoming an increasingly common problem among adolescents and has a negative impact on their emotional and social development. Research shows that there is a significant negative relationship between internet addiction and emotional intelligence, meaning that excessive internet use can reduce individuals' ability to manage their emotions (El-Gazar et al., 2024) ^[2]. From this perspective, studying how adolescents' communication changes under the influence of social media, particularly through the lens of emotional intelligence and internet addiction, remains an important research issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent academic literature, it is widely recognized that social media is playing an increasingly important role in adolescents' lives and has a significant impact on their psychological development. Studies conducted in recent years show that social media is not only a means of communication but also an important space where adolescents form their identity, express themselves, and build social relationships (Piccerillo & Digennaro, 2025) ^[5]. At the same time, the growing use of social media has become an integral part of adolescents' daily lives, and this process is closely linked to their psychological well-being. The impact of social media on adolescents can also vary depending on individual factors. In particular, the phenomenon of problematic social media use has received increasing attention.

Research suggests that excessive use of social media may be associated with depression, impulsivity, and attention problems in some adolescents (Montag, C., et al., 2024) ^[4]. It is also important to note that such negative effects are not observed in all users, suggesting that the impact of social media also depends on individual psychological and social conditions. Within theoretical approaches, Self-Determination Theory plays an important role in explaining the influence of social media. Research based on this theory shows that social media can either support or hinder adolescents' basic psychological needs, such as belonging, autonomy, and competence (West et al., 2024) ^[8]. When these needs are satisfied, they lead to positive psychological outcomes, whereas barriers to their fulfillment may contribute to psychological problems and the development of addictive behaviors. Emotional intelligence is also considered an important protective factor in adolescents' use of social media. Research shows that adolescents with higher levels of emotional intelligence tend to communicate more effectively, manage conflicts better, and adapt more successfully in social situations (Piccerillo & Digennaro, 2025) ^[5].

In contrast, lower levels of emotional intelligence are associated with problematic use of social media, which may lead to negative psychological outcomes. The relationship between internet addiction and emotional intelligence has also been widely studied. Empirical findings indicate a significant negative correlation between these variables. Excessive internet use, in particular, is linked to a decline in emotional regulation abilities (El-Gazar et al., 2024) ^[2]. Other studies further confirm that lower emotional intelligence is related to higher levels of internet addiction (Sharma et al., 2025) ^[7]. Among the different components, the ability to manage and use one's emotions appears to be especially important. Internet addiction affects not only emotional intelligence but also overall psychological well-being. Research shows that it is closely connected with impaired impulse control, which can negatively influence both social functioning and mental health (Alaswad et al., 2025) ^[1]. At the same time, emotional intelligence may serve as a protective factor that helps reduce these negative effects.

Studies conducted during the pandemic also highlight the link between social media use and emotional well-being. Adolescents with lower levels of emotional intelligence were found to use social media more excessively and to experience higher levels of psychological distress (Pino & Mastromarino, 2023) ^[6]. These findings suggest that developing emotional intelligence plays an important role in preventing the negative consequences of social media use. Some studies also suggest that the relationship between emotional intelligence,

internet addiction, and psychological well-being is complex and not always straightforward. For example, while emotional intelligence is generally linked to higher levels of psychological well-being, its connection with internet addiction is not always strong or consistent (Alaswad et al., 2025) [1]. This indicates the need for a deeper understanding of how these factors interact with each other. Overall, the existing literature shows that the impact of social media on adolescent development is complex and influenced by multiple factors. Whether this influence is positive or negative largely depends on the individual's level of emotional intelligence, patterns of internet use, and the extent to which their psychological needs are satisfied.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study aims to examine how adolescents' communication changes under the influence of social media, with a particular focus on the relationship between emotional intelligence and internet addiction. A correlational research design was used to explore adolescents' behavior and psychological characteristics in the digital environment. The study involved 520 adolescents aged 18-22 who were students from different higher education institutions. Participation was voluntary. Several methods were used to collect the data. Observation was applied to study adolescents' behavior, social activity, and communication patterns in real-life interactions.

Interviews helped to better understand their reasons for using social media, their emotional state, and their attitudes toward interpersonal relationships. These methods also supported a deeper interpretation of the psychodiagnostic results. The following psychodiagnostic tools were used in the study: K. Young Internet Addiction Test (IAT) – used to measure the level of internet addiction, particularly related to social media use; based on the results, participants were classified as “normal,” “mildly addicted,” or “moderately addicted.” N. Hall Emotional Intelligence Test – used to assess emotional intelligence and its main components, including emotional awareness, emotion regulation, self-motivation, empathy, and the ability to understand others' emotions. In the empirical stage, the relationship between internet addiction and the components of emotional intelligence was analyzed statistically. The data were processed using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (N = 520).

Table 1: Spearman Correlation between Internet Addiction and Emotional Intelligence Components (N = 520)

Variables	Internet Addiction	Emotional Awareness	Emotion Regulation	Self-Motivation	Empathy	Perceiving Others' Emotions	Overall EI
Internet Addiction	1.000	-,125**	-,142**	-,166**	-,209**	-,172**	-,198**
Emotional Awareness		1.000	,372**	,432**	,544**	,478**	,649**
Emotion Regulation			1.000	,479**	,477**	,382**	,639**
Self-Motivation				1.000	,632**	,581**	,788**
Empathy					1.000	,681**	,810**
Perceiving Others' Emotions						1.000	,749**

Note: Statistically significant at $p < 0.01$. The analysis showed that the level of internet addiction has a statistically significant negative relationship with all components of emotional intelligence. The strongest negative correlation was found in empathy ($\rho = -0.209$; $p < 0.01$), which suggests that excessive use of social media reduces adolescents' ability to understand others' feelings and show empathy. A similar negative relationship was observed for the ability to understand others' emotions ($\rho = -0.172$) and overall emotional intelligence ($\rho = -0.198$).

These findings indicate that as adolescents become more dependent on social media, the quality of their emotional communication and their ability to adapt socially tend to decline. From a social-psychological point of view, excessive use of social media limits real face-to-face communication and weakens the ability to read nonverbal emotional signals such as facial expressions, gestures, and tone of voice. As a result, empathic communication becomes weaker, and the effectiveness of interpersonal relationships decreases. This process is especially important during adolescence, as this is the stage when emotional regulation, social adaptation, and communication skills are actively developing. For this reason, studying the relationship between social media use and emotional intelligence is essential for supporting healthy social development in adolescents.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings of the study show a clear negative relationship between increasing levels of internet addiction and lower emotional intelligence among adolescents. The strongest negative correlation was found in the empathy component ($\rho = -0.209$), suggesting that excessive use of social media significantly reduces adolescents' ability to understand others' emotional states and respond to them appropriately. These results indicate that communication in the digital environment cannot fully replace real-life social interaction; instead, it tends to simplify the emotional aspects of communication. Since adolescents often rely on text or visual symbols, their ability to understand and respond to complex emotional signals – such as tone of voice, facial expressions, and body language – may not develop sufficiently. The negative relationships found with understanding others' emotions and overall emotional intelligence further suggest that as dependence on social media increases, adolescents' social sensitivity and communication quality tend to decline. This can lead to more superficial social interactions and may create difficulties in real-life communication. From a theoretical point of view, these findings can be explained through emotional regulation. Internet addiction may serve as a way for individuals to cope with difficulties in managing negative emotions.

Adolescents may turn to social media to escape stress, anxiety, or social discomfort. Although this may provide short-term relief, it can weaken emotional development over time. These findings are also consistent with previous research. In particular, studies have shown that adolescents with lower levels of emotional intelligence are more likely to engage in problematic use of social media (Granda Brito & Sarmiento Benavides, 2025) ^[3]. This suggests that individuals with weaker emotional regulation tend to use the digital environment as a way to escape from psychological difficulties. In addition, the negative impact of internet addiction on emotional intelligence has been confirmed in other empirical studies. Excessive internet use has been linked to a reduced ability to understand and manage emotions (El-Gazar et al., 2024) ^[2]. These findings support the trends observed in this study and strengthen their scientific validity. When viewed through the lens of Self-Determination Theory, social media may partly satisfy adolescents' need for connection, but this satisfaction is often limited in quality. While online interactions exist, they do not fully provide emotional depth or real social experience.

As a result, adolescents' emotional skills – especially empathy and emotional sensitivity – may not develop sufficiently. From this perspective, the impact of social media on adolescents' communication can be seen as two-sided. On the one hand, it expands opportunities for communication; on the other hand, it may reduce deeper and more meaningful emotional connections. Overall, the findings of this study show that excessive use of social media negatively affects adolescents' emotional intelligence and the quality of their interpersonal communication. This highlights the need to introduce psychological programs aimed at developing emotional intelligence and to promote a more conscious and balanced use of social media among adolescents.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study provide empirical evidence that social media has a significant impact on adolescents' communication. In particular, a stable negative relationship was found between increasing levels of internet addiction and decreasing levels of emotional intelligence. The weakening of empathy and the ability to understand others' emotions appears to reduce the quality of adolescents' interpersonal communication. The results also show that excessive use of social media limits adolescents' real-life communication experience and slows down the development of their emotional sensitivity and communication skills. As a result, they may face difficulties in understanding social situations, recognizing others' emotional states, and responding to them appropriately. Bringing together both theoretical and empirical findings, it can be said that the impact of social media on adolescent development is two-sided. On the one hand, it expands opportunities for communication and provides easy access to information; on the other hand, it may reduce deeper and more meaningful emotional interaction. Therefore, the way and extent to which adolescents use social media play an important role in their emotional development.

Based on the findings, the following practical recommendations can be suggested: developing emotional intelligence programs in educational institutions aimed at improving adolescents' ability to understand and manage emotions, as well as their empathy skills; promoting conscious use of social media by informing adolescents about its psychological effects and supporting time management skills; strengthening psychological prevention and assessment through early detection and monitoring of internet addiction; encouraging face-to-face communication by expanding social, cultural, and sports activities; providing guidance for parents and teachers on supporting adolescents' digital behavior and creating a healthy communication environment.

References:

1. Alaswad, N. K., Hassan, S. M. S., Abdullah, S. O., Mohamed, H. A. A. E., & Maghawry, H. F. (2025). The relationship between emotional intelligence, internet addiction, and psychological well-being among university nursing students. *BMC Nursing*, 24, 1341. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-025-03957-2>
2. El-Gazar, H. E., Elgohari, H., Loutfy, A., Shawer, M., El-Monshed, A. H., Abou Zeid, M. A. G., & Zoromba, M. A. (2024). Does internet addiction affect the level of emotional intelligence among nursing students? *BMC Nursing*, 23, 555. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-024-02191-6>
3. Granda Brito, J. A., & Sarmiento Benavides, A. S. (2025). Emotional intelligence and social media use in adolescents. *Revista Multidisciplinaria Investigación Contemporánea*, 3(2), 395–418. <https://doi.org/10.58995/redlic.rmic.v3.n2.a113>
4. Montag, C., Demetrovics, Z., Elhai, J. D., Grant, D., Koning, I., Rumpf, H. J., Spada, M. M., Throuvala, M., & van den Eijnden, R. (2024). Problematic social media use in childhood and adolescence. *Addictive Behaviors*, 153, 107980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addbeh.2024.107980>
5. Piccerillo, L., & Digennaro, S. (2025). Adolescent social media use and emotional intelligence: A systematic review. *Adolescent Research Review*, 10, 201–218. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40894-024-00245-z>
6. Pino, O., & Mastromarino, S. (2023). Impact of emotional intelligence on social network abuse among adolescents during COVID-19 outbreak in Italy. *Acta Biomed*, 94(3). <https://doi.org/10.23750/abm.v94i3.14468>
7. Sharma, S., Dutt, K., & Parihar, I. (2025). Emotional intelligence as a correlate to internet addiction among adolescents. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.25215/1303.347>
8. West, M., Rice, S., & Vella-Brodrick, D. (2024). Adolescent social media use through a self-determination theory lens: A systematic scoping review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21, 862. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21070862>

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №4(1)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.